

Power management control and delivery module for a hybrid electric aircraft using fuel cell and battery

Pia Hoenicke, Debjani Ghosh, Adel Muhandes, Sumantra Bhattacharya, Christiane Bauer, Josef Kallo, Caroline Willich*

Institute for Energy Conversion and Storage, Ulm University, Albert-Einstein-Allee 47, 89081 Ulm, Germany

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ABSTRACT

Hybrid electric aircrafts using fuel cells and batteries are an option to reduce emissions in air travel. State of the art concepts either connect fuel cell and battery using a direct current/direct current (DC/DC) converter or as a direct hybrid. Converters are flexible to control but direct hybrids are lighter and easy to build. A new power control module is presented which is easier to control than a system with DC/DC converters and more flexible and efficient than a direct hybrid. The new control module was developed to assure high aircraft safety criteria due to its redundancy and additional safety measures. It includes the possibility to charge the battery passively and actively from the fuel cell or by recuperation during flight reducing the required battery size. The functionality of the system was simulated and demonstrated in flight. This new concept can be adapted to power different kinds of hybrid aircrafts and offers a guideline to long-term all-electric flights since it is scalable for different aircraft sizes including single-aisle aircrafts. It is additionally usable for all kind of hybrid drive trains using fuel cell and battery.

1. Introduction

To overcome the threat of climate change, a reduction of carbon dioxide (CO₂) emissions is crucial and a sustainable energy supply by using renewable energies has to be reached. Even though aviation adds up to only 2.1% of world's CO₂ emissions [1], in the EU the CO₂ emission due to aviation is 3% of the total emissions [1] and the contribution is expected to grow as air travel increases. One possibility to use renewable energy in aircrafts and reduce CO₂ emissions, is using hydrogen fuel cells for electric airplanes.

The fuel cell can be combined with a battery, which increases the overall efficiency of the aircraft. The fuel cell powers the aircraft during the low power phases, such as cruise. The high specific energy of hydrogen guarantees a long-term flight during these low power phases. During high power demanding phases, such as take-off, the battery boosts the aircraft drive-train. The resulting hybrid aircraft using fuel cell and battery produces no local emissions, less noise and is more efficient than conventional aircrafts.

Usually one out of two hybrid architecture options to connect a fuel cell and a battery to an electric motor driving the aircraft is used. The first approach to connect batteries and fuel cells in serial hybrids was

using one or more DC/DC converters in order to control the voltage levels [2]. This is still the most common hybrid architecture. The hybrid designs and the control of their converters is still topic of research [3–8] especially for aircrafts [9,10]. The advantages of DC/DC converters are their flexibility and the reduction of criteria for the battery and fuel cell design in a hybrid system. However, DC/DC converters are heavy since they need to be in the power range of the fuel cell or battery. Moreover, they are complex to control and typically present a single-point of failure.

The other option is a direct hybrid also called passive or unregulated hybrid where battery and fuel cell are connected directly in parallel using diodes [11–14]. These direct hybrids are easily built and light, but not controllable. In direct hybrids only the voltages of the fuel cell and battery define in which driving mode the system is operating and battery charging is not possible. Bataller-Planes et al. compared an unregulated hybrid with a hybrid using a DC/DC converter and came to the conclusion that an unregulated connection is more reliable, efficient and safe and was more suitable for their airplane [15].

In this contribution an improved, unregulated power management connection called Power Management Control and Delivery (PMCD) module with a good trade-off between flexibility and control effort was developed. Most important, the system assures high safety by being

* Corresponding author.

E-mail address: caroline.willich@uni-ulm.de (C. Willich).

Nomenclature	
<i>Abbreviations</i>	
AC	alternating current
CC	constant current
CO ₂	carbon dioxide
CV	constant voltage
DC	direct current
PMCD	Power management control and delivery
SOC	State of charge
EMI	Electromagnetic Interference
<i>List of variables</i>	
C	Capacitance in F
$I_{\text{BatteryCharging}}$	Charging current of the battery in A
R	Resistance in Ω
R_{Battery}	Internal resistance of the battery in Ω
τ	Time constant in s
V_{Battery}	Voltage of the battery in V
V_{Source}	Voltage of the fuel cell or inverter whichever charges the battery in V
P_{Battery}	Usable Battery Discharging Power in W
$P_{\text{inverters}}$	DC Power flowing out of the PMCD into both Inverters in W
P_{FC}	Usable Fuel Cell Power in W
P_{Charge}	Power for Battery Charging in W

completely redundant in addition to other included safety measures. The reliability and safety of the system is an important requirement for the application in aircrafts.

2. Concept

The hybrid considered in this paper consists of a fuel cell and a battery as sources and at least one motor as load as shown in Fig. 1. Since batteries and fuel cells generate direct current (DC) while modern motors often need alternating current (AC), an inverter is used to couple an AC motor to the high voltage DC bus. The sources and load are connected by the power management control and delivery module (PMCD).

The main task of the PMCD is connecting the sources to the load and controlling the power flow and voltage levels in all flight phases to always match the generated and required power. This is necessary since the required power for a flight changes over time as shown exemplarily in Fig. 2. It can be seen, that there are high power demanding phases like take-off and low power demanding phases like cruise or descend. During descend the power can even become negative if recuperation is possible.

Fig. 1. Schematic of one PMCD branch for powering the motor with fuses F1 to F10, Diodes D1 to D3, switches S1 to S10 and PS1 to PS7, resistances R1 to R7.

Fig. 2. Required power as a percentage of maximum system power during different flight phases of a possible flight profile plotted against flight duration.

The actual values for power and time change with altitude, slope and flight time. The cruise phase, for instance, is typically longer than the other phases since it determines the flight distance.

According to the required power, it is possible to choose between different power modes based on the architecture of the PMCD. This architecture allows to connect each component (battery and fuel cell) individually to the DC-bus, allowing a flexible and safe hybrid system. The possible power modes are fuel cell mode, hybrid mode, battery mode, passive charging mode and active charging mode.

2.1. Fuel cell mode

The fuel cell mode is the main mode of the aircraft. During cruise only the fuel cell is connected to the motor via switch S1 since the fuel cell power is enough for a straight level flight. This power flow in fuel cell mode is shown in Fig. 3 as solid line. The red line is the positive path going from fuel cell over the DC bus to the inverter. The blue line is the negative path going from inverter back to the fuel cell. The battery is not connected in this mode and switch S2 is open. The fuel cell mode is used if the maximum possible fuel cell power is higher or equal to the motor power demand. This mode is chosen if the fuel cell power alone is enough to deliver the required motor power plus losses and charging of the battery is not possible or not necessary. In the following, the losses are not mentioned again but they have to be always taken into account.

2.2. Hybrid mode

Hybrid mode is used when the required power of the motor is higher than the maximum fuel cell power.

In a high power demanding phase, like take-off and climb, the battery and fuel cell supply the motor in parallel as a direct hybrid and switches S1 and S2 are closed. These power paths are shown in Fig. 3. The solid line is the fuel cell path and the dashed line the battery path.

Fig. 3. PMCD schematic with fuel cell (solid line) and battery (dashed line) mode paths. Each positive line is red and the negative blue. In fuel cell mode only the fuel cell is connected via the solid red and blue lines and switch S1 is closed. In hybrid mode both fuel cell (solid lines) and battery (dashed lines) are connected and switches S1 and S2 are closed.

The red lines are the positive paths to the inverter. In blue are the negative paths back to the sources. All lines together show the power flow in hybrid mode. To be able to connect the fuel cell and battery as a direct hybrid, the voltage ranges of the two sources need to be matched properly and the hybrid point has to be chosen adequately [11,12,16].

Fig. 4 shows the current–voltage curve of a fuel cell. For the battery a nominal operating point P1 with voltage V1 is assumed. In this hybrid point, the battery and fuel cell voltages match each other but their currents can differ. Both sources can deliver power in parallel. At the hybrid point, the fuel cell will deliver the current determined by its current–voltage curve and this hybrid point (I1 in Fig. 4). In this hybrid point the battery voltage is equal to the hybrid point voltage but the current depends on the power demand. The battery can discharge with a current up to its maximum current depending on the power demand of the motor. The fuel cell current plus the battery current equal the current demand of the motor.

If the state of charge (SOC) of the battery changes, the battery voltage and the operational point of the battery as well as the hybrid point will change. At a lower SOC the battery voltage is lower, the hybrid point moves to the right in Fig. 4 and the fuel cell delivers a higher current. Consequently, the fuel cell contribution to a constant total motor power increases over time while the battery contribution percentage decreases due to a decreasing SOC and therefore voltage. To have a useful hybrid a battery with a nominal battery voltage that equals the voltage of the fuel cell at about 2/3 of the maximum fuel cell current is chosen. This allows a hybrid point at a wide range of the battery SOC and also allows high fuel cell currents at all hybrid points.

Fig. 4. Schematic of a fuel cell voltage–current–curve, hybrid operation point and battery charging areas for the battery with the battery operational point P1 with the voltage V1 (fuel cell and battery) and fuel cell current I1.

2.3. Battery mode

The pure battery mode is a safety mode. In case the fuel cell has a failure, the battery can be used as redundant back-up power source until its energy is consumed. In battery mode, only the battery is connected to power the motor over switch S2. This can be seen in Fig. 3 as dashed line, positive path in red and negative in blue. To be able to use battery mode, the battery SOC has to be sufficient.

2.4. Battery charging

There are several options to charge the battery. If the required power for the motor is less than the available fuel cell power, the battery can be charged during flight from the fuel cell. In case the motor slows down power can also be recuperated which can charge the battery.

A charging voltage higher than the battery voltage is needed since the voltage gradient results in the charging current. If the DC bus voltage generated by fuel cell or recuperation is higher than the battery voltage the battery can be charged passively as shown in Fig. 4. If the DC bus voltage is lower than the battery voltage only active charging with the help of an additional DC/DC boost is possible. If for example the battery voltage is V1 at the operating point P1, the fuel cell has to have a voltage above the value V1 to be able to charge the battery passively. If the fuel cell voltage is below the voltage V1, the battery can only be charged actively. If the battery is charged or discharged the operational point of the battery will change and the passive and active charging areas from Fig. 4 will change as well.

2.4.1. Passive charging of the battery

If the DC bus voltage generated by fuel cell or recuperation is higher than the battery voltage and the battery is not already fully charged (SOC < 100%), the battery can be charged passively. In passive charging mode switches S1 and S3 are closed and the battery can be charged either by fuel cell or by recuperation with power flowing backwards from the motor into the DC bus. The passive charging path from the fuel cell is shown as solid line in Fig. 5.

If the inverters can control the voltage bidirectional, recuperation can be done in passive charging mode since the inverters can boost the DC voltage for battery charging.

In the passive charging mode the maximum allowed battery charging current has to be taken into account since in this mode, the internal resistance of the battery defines the charging current for each input voltage due to ohm’s law as shown in Eq. (1).

Fig. 5. PMCD schematic with passive charging (solid line) and active charging (dashed line) mode paths.

$$I_{BatteryCharging} = \frac{(V_{Source} - V_{Battery})}{R_{Battery}} \quad (1)$$

Therefore, a current sensor monitors the charging current and stops charging if the current is too high.

2.4.2. Active charging of the battery

If the fuel cell is at a high current point, the voltage is low as shown in Fig. 4.

In this point, the fuel cell can actively charge the battery with the power difference between maximum fuel cell power and required motor power as long as the battery is not fully charged (SOC < 100%). This active charging is done by a DC/DC converter.

In active charging mode, switch S1 is closed providing propulsion power. The battery is actively charged by the parallel DC/DC converter via switch S7. This active charging path is shown as dashed lines in Fig. 5.

The DC/DC increases the fuel cell voltage to a higher output voltage than the battery voltage in order to be able to charge.

In case of recuperation from the motor and if the DC voltage generated by the inverter during recuperation is lower than the battery voltage, the DC/DC converter can boost the recuperation voltage and therefore charge the battery.

Once active battery charging mode is activated and the DC/DC is connected via switch S7, the DC/DC-converter works as a battery charger and charges first with constant current (CC). Once the battery voltage matches the DC/DC output, the DC/DC converter charges with constant voltage (CV) until the current reaches values below those defined in the battery datasheet.

The used DC/DC boost converter is a one-directional converter and it is smaller and lighter than a bidirectional DC/DC for discharging and charging up to the maximum battery power or even a one-directional DC/DC for the maximum fuel cell power since only the battery charging power is flowing over the DC/DC converter. The DC/DC converter used in the PMCD has a power of 5 kW and will boost input voltages of at least 180 V up to the constant voltage charging voltage of 336 V.

The current and voltage of the DC/DC is controlled via signals from the PMCD software. Charging through the DC/DC converter is stopped every time the PMCD changes to a different operational mode since this leads to power or voltage level changes in the system or once the battery is charged (SOC = 100%).

To prevent an uncontrolled, quick succession of switching between active and passive charging modes due to small changes in the operating point, a margin can be set in the control software of e.g. 10 V for transition between active and passive charging mode. Therefore, switching takes place at slightly higher (or lower) voltages than the operating

point.

3. Electrical circuit components

3.1. Components for the mode setting

The main requirements to design the system and the components were functionality, efficiency, safety, weight and size. To allow the power modes of the PMCD and the change between these modes the switches are most important. With the switches, the mode (fuel cell, battery, hybrid, active or passive charging) is chosen. Relays are used as switches since they have low conduction losses. Moreover, the high overload capability and a safe clear galvanic isolation between low voltage control and HV connection makes relays safe [17] and therefore suitable for aviation applications. To meet the requirements of up to 480 V and 210 A, relays of type Czonka EV200HAANA are used.

In addition to the switches, the PMCD incorporates diodes to control the power flow direction. The position of these diodes are shown in Fig. 1. For instance, current flowing back into the fuel cell can damage the fuel cell. Therefore, diode D1 is used to protect the fuel cell from reverse current. The battery has one diode (D2) in discharging direction and one diode (D3) in charging direction since operating parameters for charging and discharging are different. For example, the allowed charging current and temperature (up to 150 A, 10 to 35 °C) can vary from the allowed discharging current and temperature (up to 375 A, -10 to 55 °C). Therefore, diodes are needed to determine the battery current flow direction. The corresponding switches (S2 and S3) and their control software activate the current path according to the required power flow if the battery values are within the allowed ranges for charging or discharging.

3.2. Redundancy and safety aspects

3.2.1. Redundancy

For safety reasons, in aircraft systems redundancy in the drive train is needed. To allow redundancy in the PMCD and therefore increased safety, each mode has two parallel branches available through which power can be routed from the source to the motors. There are two inverters and two motors in our aircraft to have a completely redundant drive train. The parallel branches of the PMCD can be seen in Fig. 6. For instance, S1 is the switch to connect the fuel cell to motor 1. S4 is the switch to connect the fuel cell to motor 2. S1 and S4 have the same function and supply the two motors in parallel by the fuel cell. The same applies to the switches S2 and S5 for battery mode which connect the battery to motor 1 and motor 2 and for the switches S3 and S6 for battery charging. In case of a failure in one path the other paths can still supply power. In case of a drive train component failure (PMCD component,

Fig. 6. Whole PMCD System with two parallel branches.

inverter or motor), the other parallel branch still works. For example, if the communication with one inverter is lost, this inverter is disconnected but the other inverter remains functional due to the parallel connection. In case of a battery or fuel cell failure, the failed source disconnects safely within the PMCD and the other source (fuel cell or battery) still powers the motor over the PMCD. For example, in case of a hydrogen leakage in the fuel cell, the PMCD disconnects the fuel cell via switches S1 and S4 and changes to battery mode (switches S2 and S5). Consequently, no matter which component fails, the PMCD with its hybrid architecture guarantees at least a safe landing.

More than two parallel branches are also possible to increase the aircraft power level by adding additional motor-inverter-systems and adding or extending batteries and fuel cells. This enables scalability of the system and moreover increases redundancy and therefore safety.

In addition to the previously described switches in the positive line, allowing the different modes, there are switches in the negative line (switches S9 to S12) which are used as additional safety measure in case one switch in the positive line erroneously stays closed. In order to detect a wrong switch position, each switch has a read-back signal which sends a signal to the control whether the switch is open or closed. In case of the detection of a wrong switch position, the switching signal is sent one more time. If the switching does not work at this second attempt, this line will be regarded as faulty by the controlling software for the remaining flight and only different modes can be chosen.

In case of an erroneously close stuck switch, the negative switch of the same circuit opens and breaks this electric circuit and a different mode is used. For instance, if switch S1 stays erroneously closed, S9 opens to disconnect the electric circuit connecting fuel cell with inverter1. Afterwards a transition from fuel cell to battery mode (switches S2 and S10 close) is possible. In normal operation, the positive and negative switches are switched simultaneously and therefore behave like one switch. They can have a small time delay due to manufacturing variation. In our case the maximum turn on time for a relay is 130 ms. So there might be a time delay between two switches of up to 130 ms plus the calculation time of the computer to send the signal. However, this short time delay is acceptable for the PMCD requirements since there is a waiting time of 150 ms for turning on and 50 ms for turning off and the PMCD waits for the read-back signal to be the desired value.

Each time a failure occurs during flight where a mode transition is necessary, this failed mode is stored in the system and will not be used again during the remaining flight.

The more components, the higher the possibility of a failing component. The PMCD incorporates more components than a conventional direct hybrid system. Nevertheless, conventional direct hybrids present a single point of failure. In case any component in the direct hybrid fails, the entire system fails. No matter what component fails in the developed PMCD, it is not as critical since each path can be disconnected and there is always another path or source to power the motor.

In hybrid systems using DC/DC converters a failure in the DC/DC can be critical. DC/DC converters use semiconductors, often IGBTs, which need a gate-driver circuit to control the IGBTs. These gate driver circuits also incorporate several components which add up the failure possibility, whereas the diodes of the PMCD do not need any control circuits and the relay control circuit is easier than an IGBT gate-driver circuit.

Semiconductor failures in the IGBTs, are the main failure source in DC/DC converters and often lead to short circuits [18]. The second most probable failure case is a fault in the resonant capacitor in which case the power delivery is interrupted [18]. Both failures lead to a failure of the entire system. In the PMCD, no component failure leads to a short circuit or complete failure of the system.

In the PMCD the small 5 kW PMCD DC/DC converter can fail. In that case the PMCD turns off and disconnects the DC/DC or the fuse F7 opens. The loss of the small DC/DC is not critical to the system, since only the active charging of the battery functionality is lost. The aircraft can still fly with full power and even passive charging is still possible. As with every system each component has to be chosen to have low failure rates to guarantee a reliable overall system.

3.2.2. Protection against overload

Low overcurrents are detected with current sensors in the battery, fuel cell and inverters and the software will send a signal to the switches in the line with high current and open them. Therefore, if the current value is above the allowed current for the weakest component in this line (for fuel cell 190 A, for battery discharging 600 A and for battery charging 150 A), the overcurrent is detected and the switch in this line will open. The weakest component would be either the fuel cell or battery since all other components are designed according to the fuel cell/battery rated values. On the other hand, the current has to be below the maximum rated switch current to be able to safely break the circuit. In our case the relays could open up to 1000 A safely. The software assures that opening a switch in a line with overcurrent does not lead to a failure in another line. Before the switch in the line with the

overcurrent is opened, the current power and the allowed power for the remaining path are compared. If the power is too high, the power has to be reduced before opening the switch. The power reduction is necessary to prevent the remaining line from failing too, due to resulting over-current in this remaining current-carrying line.

Since the switches opened safely and nothing in this line broke, the opened line could be used again later on. However, if it was not sure what caused the failure, it is not recommended to use the line again. Moreover, since the relay state depends on the current values the switch has opened during its lifetime. It is not recommended to use the relay again for several switching periods after it has opened a very high current like 1000 A. After the flight the relays which opened high current, should be checked and if there are some sign of degradation replaced by a new one.

To protect the aircraft from high over-currents and short-circuits which could lead to critical fires, fuses are used. Therefore, each line has its own fuse (F1–F10 in Fig. 6) to be able to break critical high currents.

3.2.3. Precharging

The DC/DC converter and the inverters for the motor have capacitors on their input side. If these systems are directly connected to the high voltage of the sources, a high current peak occurs due to the fast charging of the input capacitor. Therefore, precharging circuits are implemented in parallel to the switches S1, S2, S4, S5, S7 and S8 as shown in Fig. 6. Each precharging circuit consists of a switch (PS1 to PS8) to enable the precharging and a resistor (R1–R8) to define the maximum charging current which therefore prevents current peaks. The battery charging path does not require a precharging circuit since there is no input capacitor as for the inverters and therefore no rapid charging occurs which could lead to high currents.

The naming number of all components in one line is the same to see which mode ergo which source and load connection this component belongs to. For instance, fuse F1, diode D1 and switch S1 belong to the first line which connects the fuel cell to inverter-motor-system 1. The precharging components for switch S1 are switch PS1 and resistance R1. Since the battery charging path does not have a precharging circuit, there is no PS3 or PS6.

To define the resistor values of the precharging circuits, the charging time, maximum precharging current and losses have to be taken into account. The time for charging the precharging circuit was calculated by Eq. (2)

$$\tau = R \cdot C \tag{2}$$

With charging time τ , precharging resistance R and capacitance C of the inverter or converter. The PMCD inverters have a 320 μF capacitor.

The current I flowing through the resistance R is defined by ohms' law in Eq. (3) with a DC bus voltage V of up to 480 V. Current and resistance define the losses P by Eq. (4) as well as cable diameter and sizing of components in the precharging circuit.

$$V = R \cdot I \tag{3}$$

$$P = \frac{V^2}{R} \tag{4}$$

For a short charging time, the resistance value should be low based on Eq. (2). However, for low losses and small cable sizes and weights, a high resistance value is preferred. A trade-off between fast charging and low current was chosen for the resistor value based on charging time and component dimensioning. A 500 Ω resistor was chosen which equals a charging time of 160 ms and losses of up to 461 W.

3.2.4. Protection against electrical insulation failures

Another possibility to increase safety is the use of isometers. Isonometers monitor the electrical insulation of the system and are used to detect isolation failures. Reasons for isolation failures might be

mechanical damage if a cable runs around a sharp edge or material degradation or damages due to overvoltage. The isometers make it possible to adopt countermeasures in failure cases for instance by disabling the current path by opening the corresponding switch. Detecting this kind of failure is important, since failures in high voltage insulation can cause harm to people or cause fire in the aircraft.

To assure that each separated electric circuit is protected, four isometers are used. Each source (fuel cell and battery) and load component (inverter-motor-system1 and inverter-motor system2) has its own isometer as shown in Fig. 7.

At the same time, only one isometer is allowed to be active in a connected electrical circuit since several activated isometers would interfere with each other. Therefore, the isometers have to be activated according to the chosen operation modes, to make sure that only one isometer is activated in one electric circuit. Table 1 shows which isometer should be active in different situations. For example, if the aircraft is in fuel cell mode, the isometer on the fuel cell line (isometer 1) can be switched on which means the isometers at the inverter-motor-systems have to be deactivated since they are connected in the same electric circuit. The battery isometer (isometer 4) is also activated in this case since it is not electrically connected to the other components and the circuit needs its own isometer.

3.2.5. Cooling

Since the used components (switches, diodes, DC/DC converter, ...) all have losses, a suitable cooling system was designed to prevent overheating. Active cooling is needed for the diodes and the DC/DC converter. This is done by using liquid-cooled plates since liquid cooling is installed for the inverters and motors anyways. The liquid coolant allows a reduced cooling plate size. The battery charging and fuel cell diodes are on one cooling plate and the battery discharge diodes are on a second cooling plate since they can carry a higher current and therefore can generate higher losses. The DC/DC converter has its own integrated cooling plate. These cooling plates are connected to the cooling circuit for the motors and inverters. All other PMCD components (switches, fuses, resistances and cables) are air cooled by a forced air flow over the PMCD via an air duct.

4. Mode transitions

During operation the mentioned PMCD modes change to adapt to the required power of the load. The control software of the PMCD controls the switches and the switching sequence in order to transition safely from one mode into another. The mode transition can be done manually or automatically by the system. Even optimization of power flows and flight profiles could be integrated into this PMCD.

Fig. 7. Connection of the isometers to each possibly separated component.

Table 1
Usage of each isometer in different modes (numbering according to Fig. 1).

Condition for the isometer	Isometer 1	Isometer 2	Isometer 3	Isometer 4
Fuel cell mode	on	on	off	off
Hybrid Mode	on	off	off	off
Battery mode, battery charging	on	on	off	off
Inverter 1 disconnected hybrid mode	on	off	on	off
Inverter 1 disconnected battery or fuel cell mode	on	on	on	off
Inverter 2 disconnected hybrid mode	on	off	off	on
Inverter 2 disconnected battery or fuel cell mode	on	on	off	on

To be able to switch between modes, some requirements have to be fulfilled regarding power, voltage and current values. Therefore, the PMCD is connected to all other components via CAN-signals but all other kind of signal communication lines or direct current sensors are also possible. This allows to detect caution and warning situations. Consequently, the PMCD is able to send caution and warning messages and even to react automatically to do countermeasures in case of a failure. Therefore, the PMCD guarantees a safe operation.

To change between the described operational modes, the power is set to zero before switching to fuel cell, hybrid and battery mode. These power reductions are necessary to reduce current peaks which would otherwise occur due to voltage mismatches.

Current peaks in the system increase degrading of the switches [19], can damage components and even destroy parts of the system leading to the failure of the entire drive train. Therefore, the first step for these mode transitions is reducing the power to zero. The short power reduction for those transitions is possible due to the inertia of the motor and the gliding properties of the aircraft. After the power reduction, the requirements for the mode transition are checked. If there are any violated requirements for transitioning to a mode, the PMCD sends an error message, stays in its mode and waits until the requirements are fulfilled or any allowed mode is chosen. One of these requirements is the voltage matching. Therefore, the voltage levels are compared to check if precharging is necessary. If the high voltage DC-bus at each inverter is at a lower voltage than the connected source, the next step after reducing the power is connecting the precharging circuit to prevent high current peaks. For example, if the fuel cell should be connected at the start-up of the aircraft, the fuel cell voltage (480 V without current) is higher than the DC-bus voltage (which is 0 V at the beginning of the start-up). Therefore, the precharging switches PS1 and PS4 will be connected. Once the fuel cell and DC-bus voltage match up to a defined voltage difference (e.g. 10 V), the switches S1 and S4 will close to connect the high power paths. The precharging switches will open afterwards. Once the precharging is disconnected, the power to the motor can be increased up to the desired value. The same procedure accounts for battery or hybrid mode. In hybrid mode, the fuel cell voltage is the required voltage for precharging since the fuel cell voltage at zero power is higher than the battery voltage.

Precharging is also checked before transitioning to active charging mode. If the DC/DC converter input is lower than the DC bus voltage, the switches PS7 and PS8 close. Once the DC/DC converter input voltage matches the DC bus voltage, the switches S7 and S8 close. Afterwards the switches PS7 and PS8 open. Once they are open, the active charging of the battery with CC-CV control starts.

5. Simulation

The PMCD system was simulated in Matlab Simulink to prove its functionality. The simulation includes all switches, diodes, fuses and the precharging circuits. The parameters of these components are taken

from the data sheets of the chosen hardware components and are stated in Table 2.

Fuel cell, battery and two inverter-motor systems are simulated by the Simscape Electric Drives library. The fuel cell model uses 400 cells and has its nominal operating point at 132 A and 300 V. The battery has a capacity of 75 Ah and nominal voltage of 300 V.

A shortened flight profile is used as input to show the basic PMCD functions during a flight mission. The profile includes the startup of the system, operation in hybrid mode for take-off, fuel cell only mode for cruise and a phase in which the battery is recharged during flight. The inverters are controlled in speed mode which means the torque is constant over the whole flight. In the simulation the torque was set to be 200 Nm for each motor. The speed of the electric motor changes over time to simulate the changing power demand and therefore the flight profile over time based on equation (5) with torque M and speed n .

$$P = 2 \cdot \pi \cdot M \cdot n \quad (5)$$

Fig. 8 shows the switching sequence within the PMCD for a simulated motor speed profile corresponding to the flight profile and the corresponding simulated battery, fuel cell and inverter voltages and currents over the simulated flight time.

At the beginning all switches are open and the fuel cell is at its open circuit voltage of 480 V. The battery starting SOC is set to 40% for the shown simulation. In real flights, the battery is typically at a higher SOC level at the start. The battery however discharges to medium SOC levels during the high power demand at take-off and climb phase. Since the simulated flight profile here is shortened to demonstrate the operational modes, a lower starting SOC is more suitable to show the battery charging during cruise.

The inverter voltage is initially at zero and the inverter capacitors are discharged at the beginning of the flight profile. The first step therefore is the precharging of the inverter capacitors. The switches in the fuel cell precharging circuits connect at second 1. During the precharging phase, the inverter voltage increases from 0 V to the fuel cell voltage of 480 V. Once the inverter capacitors are charged at second 3, the fuel cell switches S1 and S4 connect. The precharging switches disconnect at second 5, so the system is able to carry higher currents.

Since take-off needs high power hybrid mode is chosen next. The battery switches S2 and S5 connect at second 6 to form hybrid mode. The speed of the electric motor rises which equals to a rising power and the aircraft accelerates. Once the battery connects, the fuel cell voltage decreases until it matches the battery voltage at the hybrid point. The inverter voltage follows the fuel cell voltage until the hybrid point is reached since the diodes cause the DC bus voltage to correspond to the highest source voltage minus losses. Since both inverters have the same voltages, only the voltage of inverter 1 is shown here. During this take-off and climb phase fuel cell and battery jointly power the motors, which can be seen in positive fuel cell and battery current. The current of both inverters equals the sum of fuel cell and battery current minus losses. From second 40 on the power decreases due to a reduced power demand

Table 2
Simulation parameters for the PMCD components.

Component	Parameters
Switches	0.2 m Ω , initial state open
Diodes fuel cell D1, D4	1.5 V forward voltage, 3.5 m Ω
Diodes battery discharging D2, D5	1.19 V forward voltage, 0.194 m Ω (average of high and low state)
Diodes battery charging D3, D6	1.5 V forward voltage, 3.5 m Ω
Precharging switches	0.08 Ω , initial state open
Precharging resistances	500 Ω
Fuel cell Fuse F1, F4, F9	629 $\mu\Omega$ (calculated from power rating at 0.5I _N)
Battery Discharging Fuse F2, F5, F10	529 $\mu\Omega$ (calculated from power rating at 0.5I _N)
Battery Charging Fuse F3, F6	245 $\mu\Omega$ (calculated from power rating at 0.5I _N)

Fig. 8. Switching sequence and corresponding simulated battery, fuel cell and inverter voltages and currents over the simulated time based on the speed profile representing a flight mission. The fuel cell switches are S1 and S4, battery discharging switches are S2 and S5, battery charging switches are S3 and S6 and fuel cell precharging switches are PS1 and PS4. The switch position is given by a 1 for a connected switch and 0 for an open disconnected switch. The voltage is shown for the full range and zoomed in to show all important parts.

in climb phase. Nevertheless, the power is still high, so hybrid mode is still used. Once the motor speed demand decreases just before reaching cruise the fuel cell and battery currents decrease which results in a higher fuel cell voltage. From second 98 onwards the fuel cell powers the motor alone even though the system is still in hybrid mode.

At second 100, the flight altitude is reached and the aircraft changes into cruise phase which has a lower power demand. The fuel cell is now capable of supplying the power demand alone. Therefore, the battery switches S2 and S5 disconnect at second 101. In this fuel cell mode, the inverter voltages match the fuel cell voltage minus the diode voltage losses. Each inverter carries half the fuel cell current and the battery current is zero since the battery is not connected. It can be observed that the battery voltage increases slightly due to a voltage recovery as a result of current reduction.

Since the maximum deliverable fuel cell power is higher than the power needed for the cruise phase and the fuel cell voltage is 5 V higher than the battery voltage, the battery can be charged passively by fuel cell. This charging mode starts at second 150 when the battery charging switches S3 and S6 are connected. The charging is indicated by the

negative battery current shown in Fig. 8. It can be seen that the battery voltage increases due to increasing SOC. During the charging phase the fuel cell current is higher than in the previous fuel cell mode since the fuel cell now powers the motor and additionally charges the battery.

Beginning from second 250, the aircraft starts descending which equals a motor speed and therefore power reduction until the landing at second 300. The battery charging current increases with time in the descending phase, since the inverter currents decrease.

At second 300 the aircraft lands and the PMCD can be disconnected.

Fig. 9 shows the currents over the switches S1 and S2 in more detail. Small current spikes can be seen during the transition to precharging (second 1), hybrid mode (second 3) and battery charging mode (second 150). These current spikes are occurring due to hard switching in the PMCD to change between the modes. This mode transition of the PMCD represented by a switching sequences could lead to electromagnetic interference (EMI) problems. Since the PMCD switches very rarely in the real system (typically one time in several minutes) the adverse effect should be small. Should EMI problems occur they could be mitigated by integrating soft-switching circuits.

Fig. 9. Current flowing over switches S1 and S2, power of battery, fuel cell and inverters and efficiency over the simulated time.

Fig. 9 also shows the power of the fuel cell, battery and the inverters together with the efficiency of the PMCD to evaluate the suitability of the module as power management strategy. The efficiency only considers the efficiency of the PMCD itself without taking into account the efficiencies of other system components like inverter or the fuel cell itself since these may vary depending on the chosen inverter or fuel cell and we want to assess the losses that are occurring within the PMCD itself. The presented efficiency is considering the losses in the diodes, switches and fuses within the PMCD and therefore it is calculated by dividing the output of the PMCD by the input of the PMCD for the different modes as given in Eqs. (6)–(8). Here the Battery discharging power $P_{Battery}$ is the usable power which is generated by the battery already reduced by the internal battery system losses and P_{FC} is the usable fuel cell power already reduced by the internal fuel cell system losses. $P_{inverters}$ is the DC power flowing out of the PMCD into both inverters and P_{Charge} is the power flowing into the battery to charge it. The charging losses within the battery itself are not included.

$$\text{Efficiency Hybrid Mode : } \eta = \frac{P_{inverters}}{P_{Battery} + P_{FC}} \quad (6)$$

$$\text{Efficiency Fuel Cell Mode : } \eta = \frac{P_{inverters}}{P_{FC}} \quad (7)$$

$$\text{Efficiency Passive Charging Mode : } \eta = \frac{P_{inverters} + P_{Charge}}{P_{FC}} \quad (8)$$

At the beginning, the efficiency is set to zero, since the small source power results in mathematical problems otherwise. Therefore, there is a steep increase of efficiency at the beginning before the PMCD is really working.

In all the PMCD modes during the flight profile the efficiency is over 98%. The efficiency is lowest in passive charging mode, since there are two diodes D1 and D3, two switches S1 and S3 and two fuses F1 and F3 in the path from the fuel cell to the battery, and therefore losses are higher. However, the efficiency is still above 98% and in cruise mode, which is typically the longest mode during a flight, the efficiency reaches 99%.

In the different PMCD modes, different components may carry different currents and therefore generate different losses. In Table 3, the values for the simulated power losses of each component are shown for specific points in time during the different flight phases. The values of the losses depend on the power. It can be seen that all components

Table 3
Power losses in W for each diode, switch and fuse at specific flight points.

Flight phase	Component													
	D1, D4	D2, D5	D3, D6	S1, S4	S2, S5	S3, S6	S9, S11	S10, S12	F1, F4	F2, F5	F3, F6	F9	F10	
End of Take-off (second 40)	201.7	78.2	0	0.7	0.8	0	0.7	0.8	1.8	1.0	0	7.4	4.1	
Cruise (second 125)	122.2	0	0	0.3	0	0	0.3	0	0.7	0	0	3.0	0	
End of Battery Charging (second 300)	140.2	0	138.7	0.4	0	0.4	0.4	0.4	1.0	0	1.0	3.8	1.7	

(except those exclusively related to charging the battery) have the highest losses in take-off mode since the power demand is highest during that flight phase. The table also shows that the diodes are the main source of losses. The diodes D1 and D4 generate the highest losses since the fuel cell is the main power source in the examined cases. The diodes in the battery discharging path also have smaller resistances as shown in Table 2 than those in the fuel cell path. Different diodes were chosen for the different paths because the battery can deliver up to 600 A while the fuel cell is able to deliver up to 200 A. Therefore, diodes D2 and D5 are designed to carry 600 A, whereas diodes D1 and D4 are designed for 210 A. The disadvantage of the diodes with the higher current rating is the weight which is why the smaller diodes for the fuel cell path were chosen.

During the whole simulated flight profile, there are no critical voltage or current peaks. The simulated drive train combined with the PMCD behaves as predicted and required which shows the PMCD functions correctly.

6. Weight

Weight is always an important aspect in aviation. The estimated weight of a PMCD hardware prototype in the 100 kW range is about 20 kg. This includes the weight from the data sheets of commercially available hardware components and the estimated weight for electrical connectors and brackets for all high and low voltage connections. This value is higher than the weight of a direct hybrid since it has more components and additional functionality. However, due to the possibility of recharging the battery during flight, the battery can be smaller which compensates for some of the weight increase.

When comparing the weight of the PMCD to a system with a DC/DC the PMCD is heavier than well designed DC/DC converters in a comparable range of battery or fuel cell power for which weights between 3.2 kg and 65 kg can be found in literature [20–22]. Since a DC/DC is a single point of failure while the PMCD offers full redundancy, the PMCD weight should be compared to two DC/DC converters to assure the same redundancy. In that case the currently considered PMCD is still considerably heavier, also because the considered components were taken from non-aviation applications and are therefore not optimised for weight. By replacing components with lightweight versions, for instance by including silicon carbide (SiC) switches there is room for improvement, which will be examined more closely in the future.

7. Conclusion

The development of the power management systems for fuel cell-battery hybrids is an essential part for assuring functionality and safety of such systems. Most state of the art concepts either connect the fuel cell and the battery using a DC/DC converter or as a direct hybrid. Hybrids using converters are flexible to control but the converter is typically heavy and a single point of failure. Direct hybrids have the advantage of being lighter, more efficient and less complex to build but less flexible and cannot charge the battery.

In this contribution an improved, unregulated power management connection called Power Management Control and Delivery (PMCD) module with a good trade-off between flexibility, control effort and safety was developed. The system assures high safety due to its parallel branches and has other additional safety measures included.

The architecture of the PMCD allows the selection of the different operation modes fuel cell mode, hybrid mode, battery mode and passive as well as active battery charging mode. The modes can be chosen according to the power demand and connect the different components individually to the high voltage bus thereby allowing a flexible and safe system. The PMCD also makes it possible to charge the battery during flights passively or actively depending on the available voltage level. If the fuel cell voltage is lower than the battery voltage charging is done via an integrated DC/DC. If fuel cell voltage is higher than battery voltage the DC/DC is bypassed to charge the battery passively. To increase the overall efficiency of the aircraft charging by recuperation is also possible.

The described PMCD was designed and simulated and later built and the functionality of some modes was successfully demonstrated in the aircraft HY4 [23] which flew in 2020.

The presented concept of the PMCD can be adapted to other kinds of fuel cell-battery-hybrids for different applications but also for different system sizes. Its development is a step towards all-electric aircrafts and general vehicles for long-term use and its scalability is a key factor for the scaling up to single-aisle aircraft and later on to electrification in all aircraft categories.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Pia Hoenicke: Methodology, Writing - original draft, Visualization. **Debjani Ghosh:** Software, Methodology. **Adel Muhandes:** Software, Methodology. **Sumantra Bhattacharya:** Methodology. **Christiane Bauer:** Project administration. **Josef Kallo:** Funding acquisition, Conceptualization. **Caroline Willich:** Conceptualization, Supervision, Project administration, Writing - original draft.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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